

Auxin-binding proteins of *Zea mays* identified by photoaffinity labelling

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Auxins [indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) and related natural and synthetic analogues] are a group of phytohormones that influence fundamental growth and development responses in plants, e.g. cell elongation and cell division (see [1] for review). It is thought that auxins are synthesized in apical meristems and move by polar transport to basal/sub-apical target tissues. The control of auxin concentrations in different tissues is assumed to be mediated by synthesis, oxidative decomposition, conjugation, compartmentalization and transport, the latter being mediated by carrier proteins [2]. However, little is known of the molecular events of auxin action and control. Auxin perception and the ensuing responses are thought to be mediated initially by auxin receptors. Binding and inhibitor studies have identified auxin-binding sites located in (i) the endoplasmic reticulum, (ii) the tonoplast and (iii) plasma membrane [3]. An auxin-binding protein (ER-abp1) identified first in the endoplasmic reticulum has been purified and its primary structure deduced [4]. Work in several laboratories including our own, and described elsewhere in this volume, suggests that ER-abp1 or a related protein may be a receptor for the auxin signal at the endoplasmic reticulum or plasma membrane.

Auxin-binding sites on the plasma membrane have been implicated recently in perception of the auxin signal (see Barbier-Brygoo *et al.*, pp. 59–63 this volume), but are also thought to be involved in the transport of auxin across the membrane [5]. Auxin transport in shoot tissues seems to involve a saturable, specific nH^+/IAA^- influx carrier although passive uptake of undissociated IAA also occurs [2, 5]. The efflux carrier is inhibited by polar-auxin-transport inhibitors, e.g. 2,3,5-triiodobenzoic acid (TIBA) and the phytohormone 1-N-naphthylphthalamic acid (NPA); responses *in vivo* to NPA correlate with inhibition *in vitro* of auxin efflux from plasma membrane vesicles, which were found to have increased net accumulation of IAA [5, 6].

To increase our understanding of auxin perception and transport it will be of importance to identify the molecules responsible for the various auxin- and NPA-binding activities previously studied in plant membrane fractions, particularly those at the plasma membrane. To do this we synthesized 5-azido-7- 3H indole-3-acetic acid (azido-IAA) [7, 8], an auxin-derived photoaffinity probe that had previously been used to identify an auxin-binding activity in zucchini hypocotyl plasma membranes [9]. Upon illumination, the azido group decomposes to produce N_2 and a reactive nitrene radical that is able to form a covalent bond with other molecules, including proteins, to which the affinity probe has been bound. It had been reported that 5-azido-indole-3-acetic acid was an active auxin, being subject to polar transport and able to induce hypocotyl elongation and fresh weight increases in a number of species, with efficiencies similar to those of IAA itself [10, 11]. In addition, incubation of 5-azido-indole-3-acetic acid with maize microsomes had been shown to reduce the number of auxin-binding sites but not their affinity; binding of 5-azido-indole-3-acetic acid could be efficiently competed for by inclusion of active auxins but not by inactive-related analogues such as tryptophan and benzoic acid [12].

The experimental procedures involved the preparation of microsomal fractions highly enriched for plasma membranes by two rounds of aqueous two-phase partitioning; these membranes were incubated in the dark with 1–2 μM -azido-IAA and kept on ice for 10 min to facilitate binding of the label (any competitors of binding under investigation were added at this stage); the reaction was rapidly frozen on a metal block precooled in liquid nitrogen and was then illuminated for 10 min using a broad-spectrum mercury lamp to effect cross-linking of the ligand with bound proteins. After labelling the samples were prepared for SDS/PAGE and the labelled bands could be visualized by fluorography owing to the tritiation of the azido-IAA ligand. Freezing of the sample in liquid nitrogen limits diffusion of the nitrene radical during illumination and thereby reduces non-specific background labelling [9].

Photoaffinity labelling of plasma membrane-enriched vesicle preparations from 3-day-old etio-

Abbreviations used: IAA, indole-3-acetic acid; TIBA, 2,3,5-triiodobenzoic acid; NPA, 1-N-naphthylphthalamic acid; azido-IAA, 5-azido-7- 3H indole-3-acetic acid; PCR, polymerase chain reaction; NAA, naphthylacetic

lated maize seedlings with azido-IAA at -196°C identified three labelled proteins, named pm23, p58 and p60, with apparent molecular masses on SDS/PAGE of 23, 58 and 60 kDa respectively. The characteristics of p60 and pm23 will be discussed below.

The 60 kDa polypeptide was identified in fractions highly enriched for plasma membranes where it behaves as an integral membrane protein (named pm60; it is not solubilized by Triton X-100 but is solubilized with Triton X-114 and partitions into the Triton X-114 phase). However, a very similar 60 kDa protein (see below) was detected as a soluble protein in the cytosol and also in the crude microsomal fraction from which it could be extracted easily (N. Campos & K. Palme, unpublished work). This protein (p60s) is present in coleoptiles and roots of etiolated maize seedlings but is not detected in mesocotyl extracts. Photoaffinity labelling of pm60 and p60s is very efficient in crude protein extracts but is poorly inhibited by inclusion of auxin competitors; 5-azido-IAA and 2-naphthylacetic acid (2-NAA) reduce labelling more effectively than other auxins or inhibitors of auxin transport that were tested, although all these compounds were more effective than tryptophan, benzoic acid, *p*-aminobenzoic acid or indole lactic acid. The p60s was purified to homogeneity from the microsomal fraction. This protein is retained in NAA-Sepharose and is eluted from the resin with auxin. Following amino-acid-sequence analysis oligonucleotide primers were designed and a polymerase chain reaction (PCR) product was obtained with which a homologous cDNA was identified and isolated. The predicted polypeptide product of this cDNA clone has high sequence similarity to p60s but is not identical, which suggests the existence of a gene family for p60-like proteins. The protein appears to be synthesized as a larger precursor with the *N*-terminus of the isolated protein corresponding to amino acid 78 of the cDNA-coding region. The current sequence available for pm60 suggests that it is very similar to p60s but differs at the *N*-terminus by retaining five extra amino acids from the precursor.

The sequence of the predicted cDNA-encoded polypeptide shares peptide sequence similarity with a β -D-glycosidase from the prokaryote *Caldocellum saccharolyticum* [13] and with a number of eukaryotic β -D-glycosidases, for example a human lactase. The similarity between all these sequences is greatest in their *N*-terminal half and also near the *C*-terminus. Using the synthetic substrate *p*-nitrophenyl- β -D-glucopyranose the p60s

preparation was found to have β -D-glucohydrolase (EC 3.2.1.21) activity, which could be inhibited by the β -D-glucosidase inhibitor gluconolactone but not by the structurally related inhibitor galactonolactone. The p60s shows a high substrate specificity in contrast with the broad substrate range of the prokaryotic homologue from *C. saccharolyticum*; p60s hydrolyses the *p*-nitrophenyl- β -D-glucoside substrate but not the equivalent galactoside, whereas the *C. saccharolyticum* glycosidase rapidly hydrolyses both. That p60s has specificity for the aglycon portion of the substrate is suggested by its almost total inactivity on a number of other very similar synthetic substrates, all of which are substrates for the prokaryotic homologue. Interestingly, three naturally occurring substrates tested, salicin, cellobiose and laminaribiose, were all poor substrates for p60s. In marked contrast all these substrates were extremely rapidly hydrolysed by the *C. saccharolyticum* β -D-glycosidase. One of the first peptides to be sequenced was from the relatively poorly conserved central region of the p60s-like protein, and was found to be similar to a region of the *Agrobacterium rhizogenes rol C* gene product, which is involved in hairy-root induction on transformed plant tissue and has pleiotropic cytokinin-like effects in transgenic plants [14]. This product was subsequently shown to have β -glucosidase activity on cytokinin glucoside substrates [15] and apparently acts by interfering with the complex metabolism of cytokinin conjugates. Although the overall similarity between p60s and the *rol C* product is extremely limited and confined to the variable central region and *C*-terminal third of the protein, the possibility that the sequence similarity reflects similar substrate specificity was tested. In contrast to its inactivity on the naturally occurring glycosidase substrates described above, initial experiments with cytokinin conjugates suggest that the p60s may have an activity similar to that of *rol C*.

As p60s was identified by labelling with azido-IAA, the effect of various auxins on the hydrolysis of the synthetic substrate *p*-nitrophenyl- β -D-glucopyranoside by p60s was examined but was found to be only moderately inhibited, precluding the conclusion that p60s glucosidase activity is auxin sensitive *in vivo*. The activity of p60s on auxin conjugates is being tested, but the natural IAA-glucosides are difficult to obtain and have still to be assayed. Present data do not allow firm conclusions to be drawn about the biochemical or physiological role of p60s and other hypotheses are also being investigated. Given the poor inhibition of p60s labelling and glucosidase activity by active auxins

and the limited number of auxin and auxin-related substrates tested, the basis of labelling of p60 proteins by the photoaffinity probe is currently difficult to assess.

The 23 kDa (pm23) protein labelled by azido-IAA is detected only in fractions highly enriched for plasma membranes. Labelling of the pm23 is optimal at pH 6.5–7.5, is inhibited by the inclusion of auxins (IAA, 1-NAA, 2,4-D, IBA and to a lesser extent ILA) but is unaffected by millimolar 2-NAA, tryptophan or benzoic acid. Interestingly, labelling was reduced in the presence of NPA and was efficiently inhibited by the presence of TIBA. A polyclonal antibody (PAB130) raised against ER-abp1 is thought to recognize a highly conserved epitope within a variety of ABPs and we found that it also recognizes pm23. Solubilization of pm23 from membranes by Triton X-100 was $\geq 50\%$. However, it was possible to extract pm23 from vesicles with Triton X-114, after which it partitions into the aqueous, Triton-depleted phase. Using this information a purification scheme was designed to allow purification of pm23 from crude coleoptile microsomes, with a 7000-fold purification. Following amino acid sequence analysis, PCR and the probing of a maize coleoptile cDNA library, a cognate clone has been identified. Sequencing of this clone revealed no extensive similarity with ABP1 and no similarity to sequences in data bases, but its functional analysis is underway.

We are also interested in the auxin-efflux-carrier system that is inhibited by phytohormones such as NPA. High-specificity binding of [^3H]NPA to maize microsomes had facilitated identification of NPA-binding sites (receptors) localized to the plasma membranes [16, 17]. The NPA-receptor proteins are only partially solubilized from plasma membranes by detergents, e.g. Triton X-100 [17]. The affinity of receptors, both membrane-bound and solubilized, for NPA is similar and the K_D values are approximately 10^{-7}M . Proteins solubilized by Triton X-100 had increased affinity for 1-NAA and 2-NAA. Further analysis of high- and low-specificity NPA-binding activities suggested that this binding site could be one conformation of an ABP [17] and that the NPA-binding protein could be part of the auxin-efflux-carrier system. Such proteins are likely to be important in auxin perception and transport [2].

Following the recent success with photoaffinity labelling to detect ABPs [9] we adopted a similar strategy to identify the NPA-binding activity in maize coleoptile microsomes. Assays involving use of [^3H]NPA to detect NPA binding are not

sufficiently sensitive to allow successful isolation and characterization of the NPA-binding proteins. However, it had been reported that 5'-azido-naphthylphthalamic acid is a competitor for [^3H]NPA-binding sites on membrane vesicles [18] and so we synthesized a tritiated, azido derivative, 5'-azido-[3,6- ^3H]NPA (azido-NPA), to specifically label membrane proteins that could be auxin-efflux-carrier components ([19]; R. Zettl, N. Campos, J. Feldwisch, J. Schell, W. Boland & K. Palme, unpublished work).

Photoaffinity labelling using azido-NPA resulted in low background labelling of proteins even at 4°C. It is suggested that azido-NPA may bind more specifically and stably than azido-IAA. It was found that photoaffinity labelling of plasma-membrane-vesicle preparations yielded three cross-linked polypeptides of apparent molecular mass 23 kDa, 24 kDa and 60 kDa. We assume that labelling of the 24 and 60 kDa proteins is non-specific as it was not reduced in the presence of millimolar auxin, TIBA or NPA; labelling of the 60 kDa protein also appeared to be pH independent. Binding of azido-NPA to the 23 kDa protein was most efficient at pH 5.5 and was competed for by unlabelled NPA, TIBA and also by IAA, but not by benzoic acid. The 23 kDa protein was detectable only in plasma-membrane-enriched microsome preparations. About 50% was solubilized from membranes with Triton X-100 and the labelled band was recognized by PAB130 raised against ABP1. This recognition provides further evidence to support the hypothesis that the 23 kDa protein is functionally involved in auxin efflux. The 23 kDa protein which is labelled in plasma membranes by azido-IAA (pm23, see above) appears to co-migrate with that labelled by azido-NPA and the purified pm23 binds to both photoaffinity probes, although with altered competition characteristics for 1-NAA and 2-NAA. Although we cannot conclude that the 23 kDa polypeptides labelled by azido-IAA and azido-NPA are identical, they have a striking number of physical and biochemical properties in common.

In the absence of direct functional evidence we must remain circumspect about the role of pm23. However, despite the difficulties in equating photoaffinity labelling with classical binding studies, the evidence we have to date suggests that pm23 may be related to the NPA receptor, and thus could be involved in polar auxin transport.

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